

ISic3594

I.Sicily inscription 3594

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

stone

Object

architrave

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

on an architrave of a door of the convent of the Padri Minori
Osservanti, on Acre monte (destr. 1693)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, (near) Palazzolo Acreide (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175586

1. Ἰέρων.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645673

PHI 175586

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 56.1103.3.1

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.70

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3594. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388788>